

Recommended citation: Schrey-Niemenmaa, K., & Jones, M. E. (2018). Challenges for Engineering Education in Developing Innovation and Entrepreneurship. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 1208-1214). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672833.

Challenges for Engineering Education in Developing Innovation and Entrepreneurship

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Conference Key Areas: Fostering entrepreneurship, Innovation as the context for EE, Attractiveness of EE

Keywords: Entrepreneurial mind-set, innovation development, educational challenges

INTRODUCTION

Both automation and globalisation of manufacturing have caused significant changes for European companies involved in engineering related activities. These have included the diminishing number of large manufacturing companies and the decreased expectation of single organisation life time employment [1]. The nature of the professional competences required today and for tomorrow is rapidly changing. In addition to acquiring core 'hard' skills in subject specialisations, graduating engineers are expected to have developed self-learning abilities, skills to combine pieces of knowledge to innovative solutions and appreciate the need to embrace at least entrepreneurial mind-set. A recent science policy report issued by the EC [2] has stressed that entrepreneurial skills and attitudes can be learned. The report even defines what the competences are and in which level they should be learned. Is there a broad

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consensus as to what these are and how to include them in curricula? We would question such a broad statement, or indeed if such a consensus is required – for example - are the needs different in different countries in Europe? The challenge for engineering educators in an already dense curriculum is to identify effective ways by which the essential elements of an entrepreneurial culture can be developed in students.

1 THE CHALLENGE

1.1 Competence and Entrepreneurial skills

It is widely appreciated that to be effective an engineer requires a very diverse range of competences and skill levels. The required mix of these and the emphasis placed on them will of course vary from position to position and indeed the individual occupying the position. As part of a complete engineering education it is important that students are introduced to key aspects of management, finance, teams, leadership, etc., with various ways employed to develop this awareness. However, with the changing nature of professional engineering positions in Europe today, the requirement for engineers to have additional competences emerges. The question then arises how best to encourage the development of entrepreneurial mind-sets in today's engineering students. Is such a mind-set needed by all students and is that sufficient or do students need additionally skills and competences in entrepreneurship?

In this context one interesting item of research was undertaken by TEK – the Association of Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland - in 2016 building on earlier work in 2014 [a]. During the 2016 survey TEK contacted 2779 of its members to seek their evaluation of the importance of various skills and competences in their present position. This was sent to TEK members who had been born in the years 1963, 1973 and 1983, thus enabling comparisons to be made with changes in age, or perhaps seniority - within an organisation. Replies were received from 544 members (i.e. a 19.6% return – a healthy response rate by any standards) Of these 74% were men and 26% women. 85% held a Masters level degree in engineering, 9% in science and 3% in architecture. The results of this survey to the question: “what competences you need in your current job?” are presented graphically in Fig 1.

Some of the outcomes as seen in Fig. 1. offer few surprises, such as the importance of problem solving and analytical thinking – to be anticipated for an individual having a technical background – and also the emphasis on communication and time management. What is particularly noteworthy is the lower emphasis placed on entrepreneurial capacities. However, at the same time it should be stated that this survey was classifying the answerers to senior managers, middle managers and specialists and therefore, by default engineers who might have established small companies of just a few individuals will probably not have been identified and they might have been a small minority. With the increasing pace of technical development and the changing nature of many companies, there is a growing recognition today, that an ‘entrepreneurial-like’ approach may be necessary in even the largest organisations. But from this survey, perhaps not unsurprisingly, it would appear that in comparison with other skills it is not of the highest priority. Do they not see the need of an entrepreneurial mind-set if they are not self-employed - or are entrepreneurial competences so common that the relationship to entrepreneurship is not appreciated or understood?

Fig. 1. Results of an estimation of the importance of the requirement of their competences, taken from the 'Survey on Continuing Professional Development' undertaken by TEK – the Academic Engineers and Architects in Finland in 2016

The highest appreciated skills were problem solving, information retrieval, time management, oral communication, team working and critical thinking – but aren't these parts of competences of entrepreneurship?

In addressing the topic of competence development previously, [3] it had been suggested that the best place and time to develop these skills is not necessarily the university. During a university education the initial foundations can and should be laid for all of these competences, but the emphasis must be on those to which the university is best suited. Examples of these are core mathematical, science and engineering understanding – without which an individual can hardly be expected to function as an engineer - and to have developed effective oral and written communication skills. Management, financial and leadership skills, while vitally important and their initial development should be started during and undergraduate education, can more effectively be developed in a work environment supported with continuing education.

Comparing these competences with the EntreComp competences [4] (Figure 2) one can notice there many similar competences required as parts of the entrepreneurship competence. It is evident that focusing in different positions and jobs different competences are highlighted but never the less it would be difficult to manage in engineering profession without the main subject based competences, value based competences, cross-disciplinary competences and interaction, internationalisation and organisational skills.

Fig. 2. A diagrammatic indication of the areas and competences of the EntreComp conceptual model

1.2 Needed competences - are they advancing entrepreneurial mind-set

An entrepreneurial mind-set is something that is appreciated in most of the positions in working life no matter if an engineer is self-employed, working in a small or large company or even in public sector. That mind-set means understanding the implications of results - in outcomes, economics, sustainability etc. Hardly any engineer can “just work”, but has to continuously enhance the results measured with different metrics.

1.3 How to teach the entrepreneurial mind-set?

Teaching in the traditional way might not be the solution to develop the necessary and appreciated competences. While lectures about financial calculations, theoretical analysis of risk management or quality standards might not encourage students to make the effort of starting their own business, that knowledge can save them from unhealthy solutions. Instead using different learning methods like problem or project based learning [5], CDIO (Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate) [6] or other ways to help students to develop the skills to solve problems, make plans, and discuss different cases from real working life can give new experiences and awake interest and creativity in producing different solutions. These learning approaches would help to create an entrepreneurial mind-set and relate this to required knowledge can lead to an overall entrepreneurial approach.

2 HOW THE UNIVERSITIES ARE REFLECTING TO THE DEMAND

The conundrum is that the curriculum is already crowded and no organisation would want to compromise sound engineering skills in its recruitment. Therefore, how are entrepreneurial skills to be developed? Furthermore how are students to be encouraged to build from the engineering skills new innovative combinations leading to products or services that can find paying customers? Are the competences needed in Bachelor level in applied sciences different from the skills needed in masters or doctorate level in sciences?

Real life projects with real customers are much talked as good way to build bridges between worlds of education and work. The challenge is to define the learning outcomes in concrete way and define metrics for them. What needs to be done during the projects to make sure the learning has happened?

According to a study where the current state of entrepreneurship education in three Universities of Technology in Finland was evaluated, the most important conclusion was that defining entrepreneurship in the context of starting a business limits students' possibilities to learn entrepreneurial skills. Few students have the will or possibility to practice entrepreneurial activities, if it is defined only in the context of starting a business. Thus for the purpose of entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurship should be defined as entrepreneurial activities that can be practiced in several contexts. Universities should support student opportunities to practice entrepreneurial activities. Offering such possibilities requires co-operation between entrepreneurship education stakeholders.[7]

In Universities entrepreneurship needs to be seen in its context - to be an entrepreneur in science is a different issue than starting a business of selling ice-cream. In science the time to develop the product, find its customers etc is much more time consuming and thus needs long term commitment and financing before it starts to pay back.

2.1 Imperial College London

At Imperial College London innovation and entrepreneurship are not explicitly included for every student in its already highly demanding curriculum, but according to a student's interest it is possible in the majority of engineering programmes to include business courses which specifically involve facets of entrepreneurship. In addition students are encouraged to participate in a diversity of non-curricular activities where their entrepreneurial skills will be developed. To support such activities spaces and facilities are made available where they can develop ideas. These spaces might include design tools and fabrication techniques such as 3D printers.

Undertaking projects during a university engineering course can be a beneficial way to help students develop an awareness of entrepreneurial skills. Within the Faculty of Engineering projects can take different forms. Some are staff-led and a well known example of these is the 'Constructionarium' project in the Civil Engineering Department. This is a major third- year project to give all students experience of a construction site. Students work in teams and live on site and are responsible for all facets of the work including safety. The projects are serious and real and enthuses students with a taste of being in charge of actual construction site. Some projects are entirely student led. These have included 'Racing Green Endurance' when in 2010 students transformed a petrol powered racing car, the Radical SR8, into a high performance electric vehicle, having two radical EVO Electric motors with no gear boxes and including regenerative braking, energy dense batteries, and a computer management system. To demonstrate the capabilities of the vehicle they drove the Pan-American Highway (26,000

km) from Prudhoe Bay in Alaska to Ushuaia in Tierra del Fuego Province, Argentina. Funds for this project were raised from industry. Another example is the E.Quinox project – a student-led engineering summer Project in Rwanda, associated with the development of a battery hire and solar power recharging stations for remote communities via the installation of energy kiosks. This involves engineering students from different disciplines working in teams with some Civil & Mech E students working in teams. The students have had to raise finance themselves but subsequently have received support from UNDP and the Rwandan government. This particular project has received the "Supreme Humanitarian" award of the IEEE. It should be clear from these examples taken from the many projects how they are contributing to the development of entrepreneurial skills.

2.2 Metropolia University of Applied Sciences

In Metropolia University of Applied Sciences special MINNO (Metropolia innovation projects) are part of every curricula. This 10 ECTS course additionally to other courses should give the basic understanding about entrepreneurship. But one can question is that enough? How to develop the entrepreneur mind-set?

In the programme of Electrical Engineering and Automation in Metropolia the learning starts in the first year with an introductory project. That is a “gaming project”, having the other students or lecturers as customers. In that project teams are in the beginning expected to produce a project plan including budget, schedule, risk analysis etc. Additionally shortly after the project has started the student need to make a marketing speech to potential customers - how to sell the product. Already in this phase students learn the basic elements of entrepreneurship.

Later on during the 3rd year in the MINNO project students are going deeper to project management - they even need to participate the national student competition of project management which might lead to the European finals.

Additionally to the courses developing entrepreneurial competences and mind-set, Metropolia offers several courses directly focusing on skills to create a company – such as ‘how to develop a business plan, how to choose the legal form of the business, what are the responsibilities and official requirements etc.

Last year Metropolia joined an EU funded ERASMUS+ project “Development of an entrepreneurial mindset in higher education” EmindS which aims to develop entrepreneurial mindset of HE & VET students based on the EntreComp competence model [4], through the application of a systematic methodology using student centered innovative approaches [8]. In the project the competences are analysed, a tool for evaluating them will be developed and finally active learning sets will be developed. This work will hopefully generate information about good practices to provide usable learning experiences for Metropolia students.

3 REFLECTION

In this paper experiences of two very different types of universities in different European countries having engineering programmes are clarified. Can we awake and add value to the discussion to find appropriate way of offering the students best opportunities to manage in the requirements of the industry of the future?

In a university of applied sciences the learning might be more practical and directed to products that have shorter way from invention to market while in a research university the

innovation or research result needs more development to find its practical, sellable form of a product.

In both of the cases project management seems to be one of the most important entrepreneurship competence. From the EntreComp competences that covers the sub-competences: Planning and management, coping with ambiguity, uncertainty and risk, working with others, learning through experience and valuing ideas.

But how to make sure that in addition students become aware of additional dimensions such as ethical and sustainable thinking, creativity, vision and spotting opportunities, which are essential for inventing the ideas and opportunities. And what about resources - as in student projects the resources can be easier to get than in real life. The study-projects are mostly rewarded with ECTS points - not with money - and the motivation is supported with the willingness to work towards graduation. Resourcing competences include self-awareness and self-efficiency, motivation and perseverance, mobilising resources, financial and economic literacy and mobilising others. Additionally there is still one competency left: Taking the initiative - which we consider to be a key element of entrepreneurship mind-set. If that is missing - nothing happens.

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